

IMPACT OF FERMENTED MAIZE OFFAL WITH MOLASSES ON GROWTH PERFORMANCE, NUTRIENT DIGESTIBILITY AND ECONOMIC BENEFITS IN BROILER CHICKENS

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess the impact of diets containing fermented maize offal with molasses as a replacement for maize on broiler chickens' growth performance, nutrient digestibility, and economic benefits. A total of 150 day-old COBB 500 broiler chicks were used in a randomized design, with five dietary groups: 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% fermented maize offal for both the starter and finisher phases. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were found in cumulative feed intake, weight gain, and final weights in the starter phase, but the feed conversion ratio was not significantly affected. The highest cumulative feed intake was in T3 (1070.37g/bird) and T1 (1043.33g/bird), with the final weights being significantly greater in T3 (1053.33g), T1 (953.33g), and T2 (945g). During the finisher phase, cumulative feed intake, weight gain, and final weight were significantly influenced by diet. T1 had the highest feed intake, while T5 had the lowest. T3 recorded the highest weight gain (1241.67g/bird) and final weight (1936.67g/bird). The nutrient digestibility coefficients showed that dry matter (DM) and crude fibre were significantly affected by the diets ($p < 0.05$), while crude protein, ether extract, ash, and nitrogen-free extract showed no significant difference. T1 recorded the highest DM digestibility (99.85%) and crude fibre digestibility (99.86%). Economically, the feed cost and cost per kg gain decreased with higher replacement levels of fermented maize offal. The study concluded that diet 3 (50% fermented maize offal with molasses) resulted in the best performance, nutrient digestibility, and economic benefits.

Key words: Fermented Maize offal, Molasses, Growth Performance, Nutrient digestibility Economic Benefits

INTRODUCTION

Maize has served as the primary energy source for the chicken industry globally for decades, comprising around 50–60% of poultry feed. Oluyemi and Roberts (2000) asserted that cereal grains constitute the primary energy source in poultry diets in tropical regions. Similarly, Ajaja et al. (2002) indicated that maize serves as the primary energy source in compounded

diets, comprising around 50% of poultry rations. Furthermore, many regions cultivate maize as a staple food for humans. As a result, there is direct competition between humans and animals for maize utilization, which has led to the current spike in corn prices. Furthermore, the elevated cost of maize has been intensified by climate change, which has caused floods resulting in significant loss

of maize farmland in several nations annually in recent years. Consequently, in order to tackle these current challenges of energy sources and costs in poultry nutrition faced by farmers, it is imperative to seek alternative energy sources that are cost-effective, accessible, and capable of fulfilling the energy needs of poultry. The inclusion of alternative feed ingredients in broiler nutrition is a growing area of interest due to the rising cost of conventional feeds like soybean meal and maize. One of the commonest alternative feed ingredients as energy source that is cheaply and readily available is maize offal (Ezieshi et al., 2011).

According to Ezieshi et al. (2011), maize offal, as a non-traditional agricultural and agro-industrial by-product, presents an optimal solution for decreasing feed costs and animal products pricing. Furthermore, maize offal is a by-product that farmers in Nigeria consistently use and is inedible for humans. Consequently, small-scale poultry farmers have used it throughout the years to augment commercial mash, aiming to decrease feed expenses with minimal consideration of its impact on performance (Ezieshi et al., 2011). Given that maize offal has a significantly lower energy value than maize, it is crucial to increase its energy content to make it a viable alternative to maize. Maize offal has been reported to improve performance of broiler chickens with significant improvements in feed conversion ratios at certain inclusion levels (Shuibu and Usman, 2024).

Adding molasses to ferment maize offal will undoubtedly increase its energy content and overall nutritional composition. According to Onunkwo and Ekine, (2020) fermentation of maize offal will enhance its nutritional value by

breaking down complex carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids into simpler units, such as amino acids, monosaccharides, and fatty acids. The process also increases the bioavailability of essential minerals like phosphorus and calcium, which are crucial for broiler growth and bone development. The purpose of this study therefore, was to evaluate the effects of feeding fermented maize offal with molasses as a replacement for maize and its economic benefits in broiler chickens.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Site

The Poultry Unit of the Teaching and Research Farm Department of Animal Science, Taraba State University, Jalingo, located between latitudes 6° 30' and 9° 30' N and longitudes 9° 00' and 12° 00' E in the Guinea Savannah Zone of Northern Nigeria, hosted the experiment. It has an annual rainfall range of 1000mm–1500mm, and the ambient temperature of the area ranges between 30 and 38°C with an average of 29°C (Kefas et al., 2020).

Experimental Birds and Management

A reputable hatchery in Jos Plateau State provided the 150-day-old COBB 500 broiler chicks. We weighed the chicks and assigned them to five dietary treatment groups, each consisting of three replicates, using a completely randomized design (CRD). Each replicate consisted of 10 chicks, with a total of 30 birds per treatment group. The birds were brooded for one week. Birds were reared on a deep litter housing system in two phases: the starter phase (1-4 weeks) and the finisher phase (5-8 weeks), respectively. Routine vaccinations and medications were strictly

Table 2: Nutrient Composition of Broilers Finisher Diets (5-8 weeks)

FMOM (%):	Treatments				
	T1(0)	T2 (25)	T3 (50)	T4 (75)	T5 (100)
Ingredients:					
Maize	62.5	46.9	31.25	11.62	0.00
FMOM	0.00	15.60	31.25	46.88	62.50
FFSB	24	24	24	24	18.7
GNC	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	1.00
FM	5.20	5.20	5.20	6.20	8.50
Bone Meal	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Palm oil	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.00	5.00
Limestone	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Salt	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Methionine	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Lysine	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Premix	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Total	100	100	100	100	100
Calculated analysis					
ME (kcal/kg)	3131.65	2989.42	2847.28	2828.26	2800.60
Crude Protein (%)	20.01	20.01	20.01	20.37	19.10
Ether extract (%)	7.58	7.39	7.21	6.96	6.03
Crude fibre (%)	3.45	4.85	6.26	7.56	8.66
Calcium (%)	1.06	1.06	1.05	1.07	1.10
Avail. Phos. (%)	0.70	0.68	0.65	0.62	0.62

Premix provided per kilogram of diet: Vitamin A 35 MIU; vitamin D3 9 MIU; vitamin E 90 g; vitamin K3 6 g; vitamin B1 7 g; vitamin B2 22 g; vitamin B6 12 g; vitamin B12 0.070 g; biotin 300 mg; pantothenic acid 35 g; nicotinic acid, 120 g; folic acid 3 g; Phytase 25000 FTU. Se 0.2 g, Cu 15 g, Fe 80 g, I 1 g, Mn 100 g, Na 1.5 g, Zn 80g, K 4 g, Co 0.25 g. FMOM =Fermented Maize offal with Molasses, FFSB= Full Fat Soyabean, GNC=Groundnut cake

Performance parameters

The initial weights of the birds were taken on arrival. The live weights of the birds as well as the feed consumption of each replicate were measured weekly. Feed conversion ratio for each replicate were determined by dividing the feed intake by the weight gain.

Nutrient Digestibility of Broiler Chickens Fed FMOM

At the last week of the experiment (8th week), one (1) bird was randomly selected from each replicate and placed in an individual metabolism cage for the digestibility study. The birds were allowed a three days adjustment period. Measured quantity of feed was given to each bird every morning and the leftover was weighed the next morning to calculate the feed intake by each bird. Faecal collections

lasted for three days. Faecal samples collected from each treatment group were bulked, milled and analyzed for proximate composition according to the procedure of A.O.A.C. (2008). The nutrient digestibility coefficient (NDC) was calculated using the formula below:

$$\text{Nutrient Digest. Coeff} = \frac{(\text{Nutrient in diet} \times \text{feed intake}) - (\text{Nutrient in faeces} \times \text{faecal output})}{\text{Nutrient in diet} \times \text{feed intake}} \times 100$$

Nutrient in diet x feed intake

Economic Analysis of Feed

In this study the economic analysis for broiler production was carried out using the experimental diets. The total quantity of feed consumed by bird in each treatment and the cost of all other feed ingredients per kilograms (Kg) used in the formulation of experimental diets will be recorded and

followed, and feed and water were given *adlibitum*.

The source and processing of the test ingredient

The test ingredient, maize offal, was sourced locally from maize milling factories in Jalingo metropolis. Molasses was purchased from Savanah sugar company Numan, Adamawa State. We mixed two (2) litres of molasses with 30 litres of water, spread-mixed it with 50 kg of maize offal, and then transferred it into an airtight polytene bag to ferment for 72 hours. Following the 72-hour fermentation

period, we sun-dried the fermented maize offal and combined it with other feed ingredients to create the chicken feed.

Experimental Diets

The experimental diets were formulated for both starter and finisher phases to meet the NRC's (1994) minimum nutrient requirement. The diets T1 (control) contained no fermented maize offal-molasses (FMOM), while the diets T2, T3, T4, and T5 contained 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% of FMOM, respectively, as presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Nutrient Composition of Broilers Starter Diets (1-4 weeks)

FMOM (%)	Treatments				
	T1(0)	T2(25)	T3(50)	T4(75)	T5(100)
Ingredients:					
Maize	51.70	38.80	28.85	12.40	0.00
FMOM	0.00	12.90	28.85	38.80	51.70
FFSB	32.00	32.00	25.50	37.50	30.50
GNC	7.50	7.500	5.50	2.00	1.00
FM	4.50	4.50	7.00	4.00	8.00
Bone Meal	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Palm oil	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	4.50
Limestone	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Salt	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Methionine	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Lysine	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Premix	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Total	100	100	100	100	100
Calculated analysis					
ME	3083.47	2965.81	2843.39	2801.24	2843.35
Crude Protein	23.03	23.03	22.09	22.24	22.14
Fat	8.73	8.57	7.58	8.55	7.8
Crude fibre	3.73	4.89	6.08	7.23	8.01
Calcium	1.06	1.06	1.10	1.05	1.11
Avail.Phosphorus	0.69	0.67	0.67	0.62	0.63

Premix provided per kilogram of diet: Vit A 35 MIU; vit D3 9 MIU; vit E 90 g; vit K3 6 g; vit B1 7 g; vit B2 22 g; vit B6 12 g; vit B12 0.070 g; biotin 300 mg; pantothenic acid 35 g; nicotinic acid, 120 g; folic acid 3 g; Phytase 25000 FTU. Se 0.2 g, Cu 15 g, Fe 80 g, 1.1 g, Mn 100 g, Na 1.5 g, Zn 80g, K 4 g, Co 0.25 g. FMOM=Fermented Maize offal with Molasses, FFSB= Full Fat Soyabean, GNC=Groundnut cake

the value will be used to determine the economics of production, with specific consideration on the diet's total intake (Kg/bird), feed cost (N/Kg), cost of total feed intake (N/Kg), total weight gain (Kg), feed cost per kilogram gain (N/Kg gain) and cost savings (N/Kg). The following parameters will be determined using the procedure of Medugu *et al.*, (2010).

$$\text{Feed cost (N/Kg)} = E \left(\frac{\text{of ingredient X cost per kg Ingredients}}{100} \right)$$

Cost of total feed intake (N/Kg) = Feed Cost (N/Kg) X Total feed intake
 Feed cost per Kg gain = Feed cost (N/Kg) X Total weight gain

Statistical Analysis

Data generated from this study were subjected to One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) using SAS (2003). Where significant difference exists among means, Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to separate the means.

RESULTS

Growth performance of feeding FMOM

The growth performance of broiler chicks fed with fermented maize offal with molasses during the starter period is presented in Table 3. The cumulative feed intake, final weight, and cumulative weight gain exhibited significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among all treatments. Cumulative feed intake was significantly ($p > 0.05$) higher in birds fed 0% FMOM and 50% FMOM, and significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower feed intake was observed in birds fed 100% FMOM. Cumulative weight gain was significantly ($p > 0.05$) greater in birds fed 50% FMOM and but significantly lower in birds given 100% FMOM. The cumulative feed conversion ratio was not significantly different across treatments, while the final weight was significantly ($p > 0.05$) greater in birds fed 50% FMOM, but significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower in birds fed 100% FMOM.

The findings on the growth performance of broiler chickens during the finisher period are found in Table 3. The cumulative weight gains were significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced by the replacement of the test ingredient. Cumulative weight gain was significantly ($p < 0.05$) greater in birds fed 50% FMOM and 0% FMOM compared to other groups. While those fed with 100% FMOM exhibited the lowest value. The final weight was significantly ($p < 0.05$) greater in birds fed 50%, 0%, 25%, and 75% FMOM respectively, but significantly lowest in birds fed 100%. The cumulative feed conversion ratio was not significantly different across the treatments

Nutrient digestibility of broiler chickens fed FMOM

From the results, 50% diet had significantly higher digestibility of dry matter comparable to the control group. This observed improvement in the digestibility in DM due to the effect of fermentation with molasses has provided valuable insights into the nutrient utilization of maize offal in broiler diets. Similarly, the crude fibre digestibility was significantly higher in T3 (50%) diet comparable to T1 the control diet. This result showed great improvement in CF digestibility of maize offal due to fermentation with molasses and this aligned with the report of previous studies highlighting the benefits of fermented fibre feed ingredients in poultry nutrition (Ginindza *et al.*, 2017).

Proximate analysis of boiler finisher diets

Table 4 presents the proximate analysis of

FMOM providing the composition of key nutritional components such as dry matter, crude protein, crude fiber, ether extract, ash, and nitrogen-free extract.

The results of the digestibility coefficient for broiler chickens fed Fermented Maize Offal with Molasses as a replacement for maize is presented in Table 5. The results showed that the DM and the CF were significantly different ($P < 0.05$) across the treatments. The other parameters CP, EE, ASH and NFE were not significantly ($P > 0.05$) different across the treatment groups.

Economic benefits of feeding FMOM to broiler chickens

The economic analysis of broiler chickens

fed FMOM as a replacement for maize is presented in Table 6. The total feed intake per bird was observed to 4.28, 3.75, 4.15, 3.87 and 3.01 Kg/bird for T1, T2, T3, T4 and T5 respectively. The highest total feed intake in Kg/bird was observed to be in T1 (4.28) while the least was observed in T5 (3.01). The cost of total feed intake revealed that T1 had the highest value ₦4312.16/Kg, while T5 recorded the least value of ₦1732.61/Kg. The highest total weight gain was recorded in T2 (1.99Kg) and T3 (1.92Kg) while the T5 recorded the least (1.32Kg). The feed conversion cost (₦/Kg gain) shows that the highest feed cost ₦2283.58/Kg gain was observed at T1, while T5 recorded the lowest feed cost of ₦1309.28/Kg gain was recorded in T5.

Table 3: Growth performance of broiler chicken fed FMOM

Parameters	Treatments				
	T1 (0)	T2 (25)	T3 (50)	T4 (75)	T5 (100)
Starter					
Initial weight (g/bird)	110.00	110.00	110.00	110.00	102.08
Cumulative Feed Intake(g/bird)	1043.3 3 ^a	833.33 ^b c	1070.3 7 ^a	955.00 ^a b	790.83 ^c
Cumulative weight gain (g/bird)	536.67. 00 ^b	470.00 ^a b	585.00 ^a	490.00 ^a b	390.87 ^c
Cumulative feed conversion ratio	1.86	1.77	1.88	1.95	2.05
Final weight (g/bird)	646.67 ^a b	580.00 ^c	695.00 ^a	601.67 ^b c	492.92 ^d
Finisher					
Initial weight (g/bird)	646.67 ^a b	580.00 ^c	695.00 a	601.67 ^b c	492.92 ^d
Cumulative feed intake (g/bird)	3237.7 0 ^a	2918.7 0 ^a	3076.3 0 ^a	2915.0 0 ^a	2214.7 0 ^b
Cumulative weight gain (g/bird)	1180.0 0 ^{ab}	1199.6 2 ^a	1241.6 7 ^{ab}	980.18 ^b c	933.01 ^c
Cumulative feed conversion ratio	2.76	2.45	2.47	2.98	2.38
Final weight (g/bird)	1826.6 7 ^a	1779.6 2 ^a	1936.6 7 ^a	1581.8 5 ^b	1425.9 3 ^b
Mortality number	2.00	1.00	1.00	2.00	2.00

FMOM =Fermented Maize offal with Molasses

Table 4. Proximate Analysis of Boiler Finisher Diets fed FMOM

Treatment	DM (%)	CP (%)	CF (%)	EE (%)	ASH (%)	NFE (%)
T1	90.95	11.13	9.13	3.25	17.94	58.55
T2	90.78	12.95	10.23	3.68	20.75	52.38
T3	90.36	13.43	10.89	3.04	20.73	51.91
T4	90.03	11.94	9.88	3.26	21.21	54.05
T5	90.54	13.13	10.21	3.14	20.41	53.11

DM = Dry matter, CP = Crude Protein, CF = Crude fiber, EE = Ether Extract, Ash = Ash, NFE = Nitrogen Free extract

Table 5. Digestibility Coefficient for Broiler Chicken Fed FMOM as a replacement for Maize

Parameters	Treatments					SEM	P-value
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5		
DM (%)	99.85 ^a	99.77 ^a	99.78 ^a	99.78 ^a	99.67 ^b	0.03	0.0302
CP (%)	99.94	99.93	99.93	99.91	99.57	0.06	0.1705
CF (%)	99.86 ^a	99.80 ^{ab}	99.84 ^a	99.83 ^{ab}	99.77 ^b	0.02	0.0498
EE (%)	99.75	99.91	99.61	99.91	99.89	0.10	0.6207
ASH (%)	99.8633	99.9	99.72	99.89	99.94	0.05	0.4307
NFE (%)	99.567	99.697	99.44	99.447	97.417	0.48	0.4815

DM=Dry matter, CP=Crude Protein, CF=Crude Fibre, EE=Ether Extract, ASH=Ash, NFE=Nitrogen Free Extract

Table 6: Economic Analysis of Production of Broiler Chickens Fed FMOM as Replacement for Maize

Parameters	T1 (0%)	T2 (25%)	T3 (50%)	T4 (75%)	T5 (100%)
Total feed intake (Kg/Bird)	4.28	3.75	4.15	3.87	3.01
Feed cost (? /Kg)	1007.27	894.41	761.29	684.78	576.47
Cost of total feed intake (? /Kg)	4312.16	3355.86	3156.82	2650.10	1732.61
Total weight Gain (Kg)	1.89	1.99	1.92	1.48	1.32
Feed cost (? /Kg gain)	2283.58	1686.36	1646.18	1786.58	1309.28

DISCUSSION

The growth performance of birds fed to dietary treatments exhibited significant differences ($p < 0.05$) across all assessed parameters, with the exception of the cumulative feed conversion ratio (CFCR). This aligned with the findings of Salami and Odunsi (2017), who indicated a substantial difference in all three examined parameters in their study. The total feed consumption of the birds increased with increasing replacement levels. This trend in the results was likely due to the reduction in dietary energy with the increase in the replacement levels,

leading birds on lower dietary energy density to consume more to meet their energy requirements (Olomu, 1995). This feeding intake pattern aligns with the findings published by other authors (Esonu et al., 2006; Ajaja et al., 2002). The improvement shown in the treatment groups and efficient nutrient utilisation may account for the increased cumulative weight gain and the final weights recorded at birds fed T3 diets. Abouelezz et al. (2014), highlighted the significance of appropriate nutrient balance for optimal avian health and performance. The palatability and flavour of the diet,

influenced by fermentation, may have contributed to the improved performance (Odunfa, 1985). Furthermore, Sugiharto and Ranjitkar (2019) reported that fermentation promotes nutrient absorption in broilers by breaking down lipids, complex carbohydrates, and proteins into simpler forms, such as fatty acids, monosaccharides, and amino acids, thereby increasing feed digestibility. Other researchers also reported that broilers fed diets containing fermented maize bran exhibit superior growth performance compared to those on conventional diets, and the improvement was attributed to the enhanced digestibility and absorption of nutrients in fermented feeds (Stefan et al., 2024). The above reports corroborated the outcome of this research. Though the final weight gain in this study was lower compared the one reported by Dibner (2011) which showed a higher final weight gain for broiler chickens using alternative energy sources; the discrepancy could be due to the impact of climate change reflected on high temperatures during the study which affected feed intake and consequently had a negative effect on the final weight gain in this study.

The economic analysis of broiler chickens fed FMOM as a replacement for maize was influenced by the levels of the replacement. It was observed that feed cost decreases as the levels of replacement of FMOM increase. T1 (0%) FMOM had the highest feed cost (N1007.27/Kg), while T5 (100%) FMOM recorded the lowest feed

cost (N576.47/Kg). Feed cost was cheaper at 100% replacement level because the cost/Kg of FMOM was cheaper compared to the cost/kg of maize. The outcome of this study agrees with the findings of Onunkwo and Ekine (2020), who used fermented maize bran in broiler diets and reported it to be economically advantageous because it allows for the use of an otherwise underutilized by-product of maize processing. Additionally, it contributes to environmental sustainability by reducing feed waste and mitigating the carbon footprint of poultry production. Additionally, the reduction in the cost per kg of FMOM in this study corroborated the study reported by Yusuf et. al (2023) when maize milling residue replaced Millet offal at 100% with a slight decrease in the cost of production.

CONCLUSION

This study revealed that the growth performance and economic benefit of broiler chicken fed fermented maize offal with molasses as an energy source was positively impacted. Fermented maize offal with molasses up to 100% as an energy source can replace maize in broilers' diets without compromising growth performance, and in addition, it can economically reduce the cost of production substantially. However, the replacement level of 50% FMOM gave growth performance, nutrient digestibility and economic benefits and is hereby recommended to farmers.

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